

Questions on Research Software Metadata for the NFDI consortia

As WG Research Software metadata, we are looking for examples where metadata for research software is currently used or developed within the different NFDI consortia. We would like to collect these examples to get requirements for a common metadata vocabulary to describe research software.

General Information

- Name of person filling out
- Contact person to follow up
- Contact mail address
- Consortium
- Research domain/community covered by your consortium

Usage of research software in your domain

“Research software is software that is employed in the scientific discovery process or a research object itself.”¹

When asking you about your domain we always mean the research domain that your consortium wants to cover.

We are interested in how research software is used in your domain:

- Which research tasks are supported by research software in your domain? e.g., data processing, data visualization, simulation, prototyping, ...
- Which types of software are typically used in your domain? e.g., analysis scripts, libraries, stand-alone software
- What examples of research software are also considered as research results in your domain?

FAIRness of research software in your domain

The awareness and importance of FAIRness for research software is being more and more recognized by the scientific community. We are interested in learning about FAIR-supporting resources for research software that exist and are used in your domain:

- How is third-party software typically cited/referred to in your research domain? (If PIDs are used: Which ones?)
- Are there any recommended practices on how to describe research software in your domain? e.g., readme, instructions to compile/install/run/use

¹ W. Hasselbring, L. Carr, S. Hettrick, H. Packer, and T. Tiropanis, “From FAIR research data toward FAIR and open research software,” *it - Information Technology*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 39–47, Feb. 2020, doi: [10.1515/itit-2019-0040](https://doi.org/10.1515/itit-2019-0040).

- How and in which situations do researchers typically search for existing software?
- Once a researcher in your domain finds a software of interest, how does the researcher decide whether or not to use it for hers/his own research?
- What resources for finding research software already exist in your domain? e.g. software repositories, directories, marketplaces. If such resources exist, please provide links to them.

State of metadata on research software in your domain

For FAIR research software, research software metadata plays a key role. We are interested in the current state of metadata for research software in your domain:

- Which domain-specific metadata schemas for research software do already exist in your domain? If possible, please provide links to them.
- What domain-specific information about research software is relevant for your domain?
- Which generic-purpose metadata schemas for research software are used in your domain? If possible, please provide a link to them.
- Where can requirements or similar information on research software metadata in your domain be found? (e.g., publications)

Artifacts developed in consortia to support the FAIRness of research software

If you plan or develop resources like tools or services to improve the FAIRness of research software in your consortium, we are interested in learning more:

- Who is responsible for developing these resources in your consortium?
- What kind of resources in respect to FAIRness of research software does your whole consortium plan/develop (not only the ones you develop yourself)?
- How should these resources improve or help to improve the FAIRness of research software?
- How do these resources contribute to improving the findability of research software?
- (If applicable) For what do these resources use metadata?
- Do you have additional information on your resources?
- Are the developed resources community-specific or are they usable by all?

Any additional information on your use case

Free text.